

Perception, Content, Generality

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Abstract

How does perceptual experience disclose the world to us? According to the *content view* (CV), visual perceptual consciousness entails representational content. According to *pure relationalism*, perception is a nonrepresentational relation between a subject and an object. In this paper, I argue that CV-theorists are implicitly committed to the claim that there is an element of generality in perception, and I show how pure relationalists would emphasise the particularity of perception, instead of its generality. But, I also argue, there are good epistemological and phenomenological reasons for thinking that there is generality in perception. In particular, I focus on Brewer's purely relationalist account and I argue that it either fails to satisfy important phenomenological and epistemological requirements, or it introduces generality in a way that makes it collapse into CV. I contend that construing the debate between CV and pure relationalism in light of particularity and generality advances our understanding of how perceptual experience discloses the world to us, as well as strengthening the standing of CV.

1. Introduction

Some philosophers think that a commonsensical notion of perceptual consciousness entails perceptual content (Byrne 2001; Siewert 1998; Schellenberg 2011; Siegel 2010); following Siegel, I call this view the *content view* (CV). There is one simple argument that the proponents of CV put forward: in perceptual experience, things appear some way; thus an experience is accurate only if things actually are as they appear; so perceptual experience has accuracy conditions; content is a kind of accuracy condition; therefore, perception has content.

According to a rival view, perception is relational, *instead* of being representational: it is a matter of a subject being in a perceptual, non-representational relation to mind-independent objects. Let us call this view *pure relationalism* (Brewer 2006, 2011, 2017; Campbell 2002; Travis 2004, 2013).

In this paper, I focus on visual perceptual experience. Thus, whenever I speak of things appearing a certain way, I mean things *looking* a certain way; I also use “perception” as shorthand for “visual perceptual experience”.

In the next section, I briefly present Siegel’s version of the argument for CV outlined above and I identify a flaw in her defence of the crucial premise. In section 3, I argue that what underlies Siegel’s argument, and the notion of perceptual content more generally, is an implicit commitment to the idea that there is generality in perception. There, I also show how pure relationalists would reject this idea, because they construe perception as wholly particular. More specifically, they think that conceiving of perception as including generality amounts to misconstruing the way in which perception relates us to our environment – the way in which perception is *openness to the world*, as is often said. In section 4, I examine the prospects for rehabilitating CV, and I argue that the grounds for thinking that there is generality in perception is that this better explains perception’s phenomenal and epistemic determinacy. In order to do this, I focus on Brewer’s purely relationalist theory and I argue that, at least in the case of the Müller-Lyer illusion, it either fails to satisfy important phenomenological and epistemological requirements, or it introduces generality in a way that makes it collapse into CV. Finally, in section 5, I argue that the same strategy that I use in connection with the Müller-Lyer illusion can be extended to a wide variety of veridical perceptual scenarios. This will significantly strengthen the standing of CV, and incidentally rehabilitate Siegel’s argument.

2. Perceptual Consciousness and Content

Siegel (2010) offers what she call the *argument from appearing* for the claim that the structure of perceptual consciousness obviously entails content.¹ The first and key premise (henceforth P1) of the argument is that “All visual perceptual experiences present clusters of properties as being instantiated” (45). The rest of the argument is as follows: given P1, we can classify experiences as either accurate or inaccurate, depending on whether the properties that they present as instantiated actually are instantiated; so perceptual experience has accuracy conditions; content is a kind of accuracy condition; therefore, perception has content.

Let us focus on P1. Siegel supports it by means of an analogy between the metaphysics of objects and properties on the one hand, and visual phenomenology on the other:

Consider the claim (made sometimes in discussions of metaphysics) that there is no such thing as a “bare particular”: that is, an object shorn of all its properties... [P1] is motivated by the idea that it is not possible for us to represent objects as so shorn in our visual experience ... For you to see a cube at all, it must be part of your visual phenomenology that the cube has certain properties: as it might be, having a certain number of facing edges and surfaces, having a certain colour, location, and so on. (Siegel 2010: 46)

Siegel’s reasoning is straightforward: there are no instances of perceptual consciousness in which objects are presented as bare particulars; therefore, properties must figure in perceptual phenomenology; but if perception presents clusters of properties as being instantiated, then perception has accuracy conditions, hence content.

In fact, Siegel runs together two ideas that should be kept distinct. One idea is that we perceive neither objects as shorn of their properties, nor properties as floating free, isolated from the objects that instantiate them. That much, however, doesn’t quite get Siegel where she wants: it only implies that we are visually presented with objects which instantiate properties, not that in perception we are “told” which properties are instantiated. This weak reading of the first premise is compatible with perception not

¹ All the main points I make about Siegel’s argument also apply to the versions of the argument for CV offered by Byrne (2001), Schellenberg (2011) and Siewert (1998).

having content, for accuracy conditions are generated only if there are specific properties such that the experience informs its subject, concerning those properties, that they are instantiated.

In order for the argument to get off the ground, a second idea is needed, namely that visual phenomenology “takes a stand” (Siegel 2010: 47) on which properties are instantiated and by which objects: “We ... see objects, and we can't seem to see them without our experience presenting them as having certain properties” (47). On this stronger reading of P1, that properties are presented as being instantiated means that visual phenomenology presents it as being the case *that* things are such-and-such, or *that* certain properties are instantiated.

Siegel's image of perception taking “a stand” on something belongs to a family of images that describe perception as *telling* us or *testifying* that things are a certain way (Austin 1962: 11), as *informing* us about goings-on in our environment the way a newspaper does (Siegel 2005/2016), and *containing claims* about the world (McDowell 2009: 11). These images contrast with others that characterise our senses as *dumb* (Austin 1962: 11), or *silent* (Travis 2004). To some, it might seem strange to describe perception almost in a personified fashion as taking a stand, testifying, etc. However, the point of these images is that the representing allegedly constitutive of perception does not consist in the subject representing to herself that things are a certain way on the basis of what sensory awareness affords her, as when one represents to oneself that someone has entered, when one sees footprints on the doorstep. In this latter case, the representing is done by the subject, who takes a certain configuration of reality (a set of footprints) to indicate that something is the case (that someone has entered). The idea of CV, by contrast, is that the representing is something that happens in perception, and insofar as the perceptual experience itself comes with the representational content that, say, *a* is F, it seems legitimate to say that perception takes a stand on the fact that *a* is F;² the *subject* may then decide whether or not to take at face value that content and endorse it in judgement.³

² See also Travis's distinction between *autorepresentation* and *allorepresentation* (2004).

³ E.g., McDowell (1994: 11).

The problem with Siegel's argument is that she doesn't consider the possibility that one might accept the first idea (we perceive objects which instantiate properties) while rejecting the second, for she seems to think that the only way in which properties can figure in perceptual experience is by them being presented as being instantiated, that is, by perception taking a stand on their being instantiated. This leads her to presenting her opponent with a false choice: either buy her conception of phenomenal character and the inextricably linked notion of content, or end up with the barely understandable claim that we perceive objects as shorn of properties. Siegel would need to provide an argument for getting from the weak to the strong interpretation of P1, but since she conflates the two, she is not in a position to do so.⁴

I take it that this shows that P1 is not adequately supported, not that it is false. This leaves us with the question: what could establish its truth or falsity? In the next section, I argue that the question hinges on whether there is an element of generality in perception.

3. Particularity and Generality

There are several things that might be referred to as the *particularity of perception*, but I have in mind a specific sense of the locution – one on which there is a putative contrast between, on the one hand, objects of perception such as particular material objects, property-instances and events, and, on the other hand, what Travis calls *generalities* (2013), which are contents of thought. To anticipate a little: from a purely relationalist perspective, the problem with the argument from appearing is that its first premise surreptitiously introduces an element of generality into the domain of perception, thereby unduly replacing the objects of perception with contents of thought.

To adapt an example from Travis (2013), suppose that John is walking, and that Pia enjoys a perceptual experience of him. Pia sees *John walking*: the object of her experience is a particular event consisting of John walking. Would it also be correct to say that Pia sees *that John is walking*? My question is not whether Pia could come to

⁴ Ivanov (2017) and Raleigh (2015) make a similar point.

know by visual means that John is walking, but rather whether Pia can see that John is walking in the sense that she perceptually experiences *that John is walking*. According to the interpretation that I offer of the debate, a pure relationalist should say that, as far as perceptual experience is concerned, Pia can only see *John walking*: “If Pia saw *that* John was walking, ‘see’ no longer speaks of the visual” (Travis 2013: 838). The reason why, from a purely relationalist perspective, one can only see *John walking*, is the following: *John walking* is a particular, spatiotemporally located event, thus something perceivable. In contrast, *That John is walking* is a general condition, so is a content of thought. In what follows, I elaborate on this point.

That John is walking is a general condition which can hold of many different particular events (i.e., an event in which John walks slowly or one in which he walks quickly, an event in which he is wearing a red shirt or one in which he wears a blue one, etc.). To see that John is walking requires bringing a particular event under the generality, i.e., it requires perception to take a stand on whether what one sees is a way (one among indefinitely many) for things to be such that John is walking (rather than, say, jumping, or running). To see *John walking*, by contrast, does not require one to bring this particular event under the general condition (indeed, it is plausible that some perceivers, e.g., infants, could see John walking without having the cognitive ability to grasp that John is walking).

The main relationalist thought is that perceiving as such does not involve bringing particular events under general conditions, because perception is, as it is sometimes said, *openness to the world*. The image of perception as openness to the world has been popularised by McDowell (1994), but pure relationalists such as Brewer and Travis make a quite specific use of that image. According to pure relationalists, perception simply brings our surroundings in view, thus putting us in contact with the here-and-now. However, perception does not take a stand on whether things are a certain way, thereby informing the experiencing subject that things fall under this or that generality; perception simply affords one sensory awareness of particulars, and then it is up to the subject to take a stand on which generality those particulars fall under. Thus, for example, Brewer writes that CV trades “direct openness to the elements of physical

reality themselves, for some intellectual act of classification or categorization” (2006: 174), and he says in a critical voice that in order for CV to be true “perception must begin by making a selection” among several ways that an object is or might be taken to be, and categorise that object as being “a specific general way, F” (2011: 79). Again, Travis says that it is “no part of what perception is – of how it opens our surroundings to our view – that in perceiving one is to appreciate one set of facts as to what things look like, and ignore others” (2004: 73).

To continue our example, suppose it looks like John is stumbling at every step. For all the perceivable features of what Pia sees, she might categorize the event as one of John dancing, or one of John being drunk, or sick, or one of John practicing a silly walk, as in a famous Monty Python sketch. Depending on what she has in mind at the moment, what she knows of John, and maybe her judgmental character, she might get the impression that he is drunk, although in fact what she sees is *John practicing a silly walk*. But all these factors that contribute to her getting the impression that she does are not strictly perceptual; perceptual phenomenology “lies in what one witnesses” (Travis 2013: 840), and what Pia witnesses is just that: *John practicing a silly walk*. However, in order for her to see, in the sense of *perceptually experiencing*, that that is what he is doing, perception would have to take a stand on whether that is what John is doing, and this is not what perception does.⁵

In light of the considerations above, we can appreciate not only that one can deny the first premise of Siegel’s argument without ending up with an absurd view of perceptual consciousness, but also *why* one may want to deny it. Siegel believes that the structure of perceptual consciousness has to be described by saying that perception presents clusters of properties *as* being instantiated. A veridical experience of John walking, for example, would present the individual *John* as instantiating the property *walking*. This, however, is as general as the propositional content *that John is walking*. For in order for Siegel to be right, perception should tell us which property is instantiated, that is, it

⁵ It would be easy to construct analogous examples involving more basic, uncontroversially perceptible properties such as colour, shape and size. I analyse such cases in section 5, and argue that, if correctly described, they reveal an important resource for CV.

should tell us what generality a particular event falls under. But again, if pure relationalism is correct, this is not how perception discloses the world to our view.

We have found a reason why one may want to resist the argument from appearing: in order to respect the insight that perceptual experience is of particulars, not generalities. So it turns out that if one wants to defend the idea that perceptual consciousness entails content, one has to defend the idea that there is generality in perception. In the next section, I examine the prospects for a CV response, and I argue that the grounds for thinking that there is generality in perception are that this would better explain perception's phenomenal and epistemic determinacy.

4. Perception and Generality

One way of rehabilitating the notion of perceptual content is to show that there are good reasons for thinking that there is generality in perception. My strategy is as follows: first, I formulate two requirements about the phenomenal and epistemic determinacy of perception that any theory of perception should be able to accommodate; second, I argue that, to fulfil these requirements, a theory has to acknowledge that there is generality in perception.

Phenomenological requirement: a perception of an object, *o*, by a subject, *S*, determines a suitably narrow range of look-statements of the form “*o* looks *F*” that would be appropriate for *S* to make on the basis of her experience.

Epistemological requirement: a perception of an object, *o*, by a subject, *S*, determines a suitably narrow range of properties that would be rational for *S* to attribute to *o* on the basis of her experience.

CV seems in line with the two requirements. According to CV, perception presents certain clusters of properties as being instantiated, so an object will look to have precisely the properties that perception (visually) presents as being instantiated by it.

And to the extent that *o* looking F rationalizes predicating F-ness of *o*, it will be rational for someone to predicate of an object a property that the object looks to have.

But are pure relationalists committed to satisfying the two requirements? Here it is worth pointing out that Bill Brewer, who has put forward the most developed purely relationalist account of looks, emphasises that despite there being, for any perception of an object *o*, “[v]arious truths of the form ‘*o* looks *F* to *S*’” (2017:221), there are also “limits beyond which an object fails to be presented in perception regardless of its role in causing an experience in which there looks to be something thus and so out there” (2011: 74). For example, “although a rabbit curled up on the chair ... may look like a cat or a cushion, that very animal could not normally look like the Eiffel Tower” (73); again, although two lines in a diagram may look unequal although they are equal, one could not have an experience *of* those lines whereby they look like a perfect circle – such an experience would be “at best a hallucination that may in some way be caused by the presence of the...diagram” (75).

Apart from what individual philosophers say, the motivation for the two requirements is general. Let us consider the phenomenological requirement first. I take it that people with normal vision have a general understanding of how things of certain kinds usually look, or can look: for example, we understand that a circle seen at a slant does not look exactly the same as when it is seen from above.⁶ This understanding underpins our ability to “convey information to each other ... about the looks of objects” (2010: 161). Our capacity to exchange information about looks is manifested in various ways. For instance, I can ask you to fetch me a specific suitcase from a room full of suitcases, and you will be able to do so because I have described how it looks and you understand my description and use it to pick out the right suitcase. Or you can teach me how to recognise birds of a certain kind by drawing my attention to the distinctive shape of the animal’s bill, the colour of the plumage, and so on. All this suggests that there is a range of things that we consider correct to say about objects’ looks and that we can roughly agree on the boundaries of this range.

⁶ See also Martin for a general statement of this point: “it is common knowledge among us that others who have normal vision know the looks associated with properties they know of through vision” (2010: 161).

Let us now turn to the epistemological requirement. I take it that perceptual experience is a fundamental source of knowledge, and that appearances play a pivotal role in making this knowledge possible: believing that something is a blue mug because it looks that way is in most circumstances a perfectly acceptable epistemic stance. However, if a blue mug might just as easily look like a dish, a knife or an airplane, we would not find this kind of explanation of someone's beliefs compelling. In this connection, Ginsborg further claims that perception can only rationalise belief if it presents objects as having some general properties:

Perception of an object cannot rationalize belief ... unless it presents the object as being a certain way, that is, as having a certain general property or feature (Ginsborg 2011: 135).

An intuitive way of developing Ginsborg's line of thought would be as follows: if you see *John walking fast*, it seems that the logical way in which that episode of seeing can rationalize the belief that, say, John is late, or even the noninferential belief that John is walking fast, is by the property *walking fast* being presented as being instantiated by John in your experience. If you see John walking, but, as far as your experience goes, John might be driving an airplane, taking a nap or writing poetry, your experience would be epistemically vacuous.

Can pure relationalism meet the requirements? In the next subsection, I present Brewer's account of looks. In subsection 4.2, I argue that Brewer has to acknowledge that, at least in one case, generality figures in perception in a way that is not compatible with the most basic commitments of his own theory. Finally, in section 5, I argue that there are good reasons for thinking that generality is always present in perception.

4.1 Brewer's *object view*

Bill Brewer (2006, 2011, 2017) has articulated a sophisticated version of pure relationalism which he calls the *object view* (henceforth OV). OV holds that perception "consists most fundamentally in a relation of conscious acquaintance with particular direct *objects*" (Brewer 2011: xi, emphasis mine), and he is clear that properties are *not*

“on a par with the object themselves” (2011: 81). Furthermore, the notion of a “perceptual relation between perceivers and the mind-independent physical objects in the world around them is ... more basic than [the notion of] representational content” (2011:62). More in detail: according to Brewer, perceptual experience fundamentally consists in a relation of conscious acquaintance “with the objects around us *from a given spatiotemporal point of view and in certain specific circumstances of perception*” (2017: 216); focusing on vision, the idea is that perceptual experience is fundamentally a question of “being visually acquainted with a particular mind-independent material object from a given spatiotemporal point of view and in certain specific circumstances” (216).

The first thing to notice is that there is no mention of either properties or appearances in the characterisation of perception offered by Brewer. One might wonder how OV could possibly satisfy the phenomenological and the epistemic requirement, then: if perception is a nonrepresentational relation to an *object*, it might seem as though Brewer is committed to the implausible claim that objects don’t appear some way in perception, and hence that perception presents objects as “shorn of their properties”, as Siegel puts it. And, *prima facie*, things don’t look bright with respect to the epistemology of perception either: it is not obvious how simply seeing an object would make it rational to believe certain things but not others about it.

In fact, Brewer has a sophisticated and nuanced account both of appearances and of the epistemic role of perception. Brewer acknowledges that, if one consciously sees an object *o*, *o* will look some ways to one; this, in turn, explains the rationality of property-attributions. Let us take in turn the phenomenological and the epistemological aspects of OV. Brewer distinguishes two ways in which an object can look F: it can *thinly* look F, or *thickly* look F:

...*o* looks F iff *o* is the direct object of a visual experience from a point of view and in circumstances relative to which *o* has visually relevant similarities with paradigm exemplars of F. I will say in such cases *o* *thinly* looks F. *O* *thickly* looks F iff *o* *thinly* looks F and the subject recognizes it *as an* F, or registers its visually

relevant similarities with paradigm exemplars of F in an active application of that very concept. (Brewer 2011: 121—122)

Thus an object *o* *thinly* looking F is a question of *o*'s visually relevant similarities to other things. *O*'s *thickly* looking F is a question of *o*'s thinly looking F plus conceptual registration on the subject's part. All this raises the question of when it is correct to say that *o* has visually relevant similarities to paradigm exemplars of Fs. Here is how Brewer characterizes visually relevant similarities:

...visually relevant similarities are identities in such things as the way in which light is reflected and transmitted from the objects in question, and the way in which stimuli are handled by the visual system, given its evolutionary history and our shared training during development. (Brewer 2011: 103)

And paradigm exemplars of F-things are defined as follows:

... instances of the kinds in question, whose association with the terms for those kinds partially constitutes our understanding of those terms, given our training in the acquisition of the relevant concepts. (104)

An example might help to get the gist of the account. Suppose you see a yellow lemon, which looks F (where F is a complex predicate that includes *yellowness*, *sphericity*, *rough texture*...). Now, the lemon looking F is a question of its similarities to paradigm exemplars of things that are yellow, spherical, and rough in texture. Thus, although perception is most fundamentally a relation of acquaintance with an *object*, not its properties, it can be made intelligible how it looks F in terms of the similarities, and registration thereof, that it has with other Fs.

The notion of visual similarities also plays a central role with respect to epistemological concerns. Brewer holds that object-perception is epistemically significant in that it acquaints us with “the grounds of empirical truth” (2011: 143), in the sense that it makes us aware of the truth-maker of a target proposition *p* that we can come to know through perception – it cannot be the case, for example, that I see John walking and the

proposition that John is walking is false.⁷ Brewer is also explicit that, although acquaintance with a particular is the fundamental *explanans*, knowledge that *o* is F “depends upon far more than mere visual acquaintance with *o*” (2011: 144). It is here that the notion of visual similarities becomes relevant: to have propositional knowledge that *o* is F, one needs, in addition to being acquainted with *o*, also (i) “register *o*’s visually relevant similarities with paradigm exemplars of F conceptually” (which amounts to *o* thickly looking F to one) (144), and (ii) “actually make the judgment that *o* is F” (145); furthermore, of course, (iii) *o* must actually be an F-thing. If acquaintance and conditions (i)-(iii) obtain, one has knowledge. If *o* is not an F-thing, but one is acquainted with *o* and conditions (i)-(ii) obtain, it is rationally intelligible why one came to mistakenly apply to *o* the predicate *being F* in light of *o*’s visually relevant similarities to F-things.

At this point, one might wonder how deep the disagreement between CV and OV really is. CV says that perception presents properties as being instantiated. OV says something *prima facie* very different, namely that perception consists in being acquainted with an object. However, OV acknowledges that, for any object *o* of acquaintance, there are several truths of the form *o* looks F, and it might seem a small step to go from there to saying that perception presents *o* as instantiating F-ness, G-ness, and so on. Consider, again, a subject who has a visual experience of a yellow lemon. According to CV, a veridical experience would present yellowness as being instantiated. According to OV, the perceived object would look like a yellow lemon to the subject, and it seems legitimate to rephrase this by saying that, according to OV, the subject’s perception presents yellowness as being instantiated by the lemon. Indeed, Brewer himself acknowledges that perception always involves “content-like aspects” (2017: 220) and that “[v]arious truths of the form ‘*o* looks *F* to *S*’ are [OV’s] recognition of what (CV) elucidates in terms of *S* (visually) experientially entertaining the content that *o* is *F*” (221).

In fact, the differences are significant. First, there is a formal difference: according to CV, perceptual experience consists in the event of a subject being presented with

⁷ See also Kalderon (2011).

properties as instantiated. OV says that *if* a S subject consciously sees *o*, then *o* looks some ways to S. The crucial thing is that, for OV, the antecedent is explanatorily prior to the consequent, and while it might be convenient to express the relation between acquaintance and looks in the form of a plain material conditional, it is clear that Brewer has in mind a metaphysically more demanding notion, such as grounding.⁸

Second, by OV's lights, saying that an object looks like a lemon to someone, and in that sense is presented as a lemon, is to give only one of a number of equally legitimate characterisations of the experience. Brewer repeatedly states that there is no such thing as a "*single* uncontroversial notion of visual phenomenology" (2011: 123) and that there are "*various* ways" (2011: 44, *emphases mine*) in which any one object of perception, in any given set of circumstances, appears (thus, *various* truths of the form "*o* looks F").

In recent work, Brewer has made this point by saying that thin looks are "massively varied and multiply nested" (2017: 220). Thus, a splash of paint may "simultaneously (thinly) look red, bright red, scarlet, shade r_{27} , ... zig-zag, snake-like, the shape of a crotchet (quarter-note) rest", and so on (220). Prior to the active registration of a particular look and the application of a corresponding concept, all the look-truths are on a par: an object of acquaintance (thinly) looks like each and every one of the things specified by a last large list of predicates.

By contrast, according to CV, any given perception comes with a fully-formed, unique content, without any need for a more basic, contentless perceptual relation. In the case of a splash of paint, for example, it would have to be part of the nature of perception that it serves up "single colour and shape predicates" (2017: 220) such as, say, *being scarlet* and *having a zig-zag shape*, thus there would have to be in perception a selection from among a large number of facts as to how the splash of paint looks.

In this connection, Brewer argues that OV is in fact *better* placed than CV to make sense of the content-like aspects of perception. The reason why has to do, again, with the variety of look-related truths. OV has an explanation for why an object *o* looks the

⁸ E.g., 2011: 69.

ways that it does: if one sees *o*, the thin looks that pertain to it are determined by the visually relevant similarities that *o* has to paradigms of various kinds of objects, given a spatiotemporal point of view and other circumstances of perception. Our ordinary looks-talk arguably relates to thick looks, because when we say that *o* looks F, we attend to, conceptually register and explicitly convey one particular look. But the selection of one particular look from among many is intelligible in virtue of (i) the subject being presented with *o* and its *various* thin looks, and (ii) the subject's "experience to date, her interests and projects at the time, and so on: upon which questions she is posing of the object of her perception on that occasion" (2017: 220). As a result of the subject interrogating the world, particular facts as to how things look become salient for her, and that is how it comes about that a particular object *o* thickly looks F to her. CV's only explanatory resource, by contrast, is a "flat and one-dimensional appeal to specific experientially entertained contents simply served up to the subject by the system" (2017: 220); in other words, a particular look would have to be picked out *before* the subject explores and interrogates the world with specific questions and interests. Thus, the argument goes, CV can neither explain the variety of an object's looks, nor why an experiencing subject might register one look rather than another.

It appears, *pace* Siegel, that someone who does not endorse CV still has a story to tell about the phenomenology and the epistemology of perception. I'm not convinced that the story is compelling, though. In the next subsection, I argue that there is at least one case in which Brewer faces a dilemma: either he fails to satisfy the phenomenological and epistemological requirements laid out above, or he introduces generality in perception in a way that is not compatible with the conception of perception at the root of purely relationalist theories.

4.2 Perception, Illusion, Generality

First of all, we should note that Brewer's point against CV is not irresistible. For one thing, although it is right that looks are massively varied and multiply nested, that does not mean that all of the looks that an object has in circumstances C are equally entitled to figure in the content of a perception of that object under C. To illustrate the point, let

us take the case of colour: a splash of paint may look coloured, red, scarlet, shade r_{27} , and so on. Normally, we experience something as having a determinate colour, not *some* colour or other. Thus, *coloured* is not in a good position to stake a claim to indexing perceptual content. Just what degree of determinateness belongs to perceptual content is presumably a function of the acuity of the individual subject's sensory system, of environmental conditions such as lighting and distance, and other subjective factors such as fatigue or attention. It might be that, when I am well rested and in a well-lit room, *o*'s r_{27} look determines the content of my experience; when I'm tired and looking at *o* in a dim light, I can only pick up on *o*'s red look. More generally: the CV-theorist can say that the look that indexes content with respect to a property of an object on a given occasion is the look that corresponds to the maximally determinate property that a subject discriminates in a given situation. Thus, although it is true that several look-statements apply to any one object of perception, it is not a mystery that one look in particular should determine content: it is a question of the properties of the object and a series of contingent conditions, both environmental and subjective.

Increasingly, it is not even clear that, if CV is true, there has to be *one* look that indexes perceptual content with respect to a particular property on any one occasion. There is no obstacle in principle to an experience representing a splash of paint as coloured, red, and scarlet all at the same time. In fact, if content is construed in terms of accuracy-conditions, then an experience accurately representing an object as being shade of red r_{27} entails that the object is red and coloured. If not only the lowest determinate discernible under given circumstances, but also higher determinables make it into perceptual content, so to speak, that simply means that perceptual content is very rich, not that there is an insurmountable problem for CV.

It might seem that the debate between CV and OV has reached a standoff. However, I think that Brewer's view faces a problem. My charge against OV is that the whole idea of *visually relevant similarities to paradigm exemplars* is afflicted by an internal tension. One pole of the tension is *visually relevant similarities*, the other is *paradigm exemplars*. To appreciate what this tension consists in, we need to investigate the notions of visually relevant similarities and paradigm exemplars with respect to their

respective nature, their respective function in the theory, and with respect to how they interact with one another in the explanation of illusion.

Visually relevant similarities are a purely empirical matter: *o*'s similarities to other things are determined by factors such as *o*'s intrinsic features, certain quantitatively describable circumstances of perception, the laws of optics and the constitution of the experiencing subject's visual system. Further, given how similarities are defined, any one object will have similarities with countless other things: a yellow lemon, for example, has visually relevant similarities to a yellow lemon, a golf ball under a yellow light, an orange under a certain other light, and so on.

The notion of paradigm exemplars, on the other hand, is normative, insofar as it is defined in terms of the appropriate conditions for the acquisition and intelligible application of an empirical concept. If, for example, you are trying to acquire the concept *equality in length*, and I show you the Müller-Lyer diagram, I am not being very helpful: that is not a paradigmatic case of equality in length, because it is not an instance of equality in length whose association with the expression "equality in length" partly constitutes our understanding of that expression. Thus, whether some F-object is a paradigm exemplar of F-things is not determined by purely empirical matters such as light reflection and stimuli. It also depends on whether the object can be deemed to satisfy a certain *general*, normative condition – the condition of being a paradigmatic F-thing.

Let us now consider the respective function of the two notions in the theory. The notion of visually relevant similarities explains how in perception we are open to the world, on the particular conception of openness endorsed by pure relationalists – one which rules out content. Visually relevant similarities allow Brewer to account for the fact that objects look some way, without having to buy Siegel's view of perceptual consciousness.

The notion of paradigm exemplars, on the other hand, ensures that the account can respect the phenomenal and epistemic determinacy present in perception. Serious

problems would affect OV without that notion. To see these problems, one only needs to consider a case of illusion and bear in mind that the similarity is symmetrical and reflexive.

Consider the Müller-Lyer diagram (henceforth ML): if, as Brewer suggests, the lines look unequal because the diagram is similar to a diagram in which the lines actually are unequal, then the lines in this latter diagram should look equal, for the diagram would be similar to ML, where the lines are in fact equal in length.⁹ Similarity is also reflexive. However, if ML is similar to itself, and looks are a question of similarities, then the lines should look equal in length. All this is readily acknowledged by Brewer to be an “unacceptable consequence” (2011: 106).

The notion of paradigm exemplars blocks these consequences, because while it is true that plain similarity is symmetrical and reflexive, *similarity to a paradigm* is not: the lines in ML look unequal because the diagram is similar to a *paradigmatic* case of inequality in length. But ML is not a paradigmatic case of equality in length, therefore the pair of lines to which ML is similar is not itself similar to ML. Thus, the notion of paradigm exemplars is crucial in securing the determinacy necessary to exclude odd phenomenological and epistemological predictions.

In what follows, I argue that Brewer faces an important challenge that can be presented in the form of a dilemma: Brewer may have *either* openness to the world as construed by pure relationalism, *or* phenomenal and epistemic determinacy, not both. To anticipate: visually relevant similarities secure openness to the world, because they are objectively determined by how an object is, plus the conditions in which it is perceived and other empirical factors. The whole spectrum of similarities that an object has to other objects given certain circumstances is perceptually present to one simply in virtue of seeing the object in question under the relevant circumstances. However, the notion of visually relevant similarities on its own does not guarantee a degree of determinacy sufficient to satisfy the phenomenological and epistemological requirements. If Brewer avails himself of the notion of paradigm exemplars, he can have the required

⁹ See Brewer (2011, ch. 5) for OV’s general treatment of illusion.

determinacy. However, he loses openness to the world as construed by pure relationalism, or so I am about to argue.

The role of paradigm exemplars is to restrict the otherwise indefinitely extended range of relevant similarities, narrowing it down to those similarity-relations that satisfy a certain general requirement: that the objects with which the object of acquaintance has similarities be suitable exemplars for the acquisition and intelligible application of a relevant concept. The very extent to which the similarities that an object has to other objects determine the ways the object looks, even at the level of *thin looks*, depends on this general element.

Paradigm exemplars imply selective categorization, for in perceptual experience a similarity-relation to a *paradigm* exemplar must be selected from among an indefinitely extended range of similarities. The ML case helps to make the point vivid. Brewer tells us that the lines in ML look unequal because the diagram is similar to a diagram constituted of two unequal lines. Now, one might think that, since similarity is reflexive, the two lines in ML should look equal in length. But no: the reflexive similarity of ML does not count, for it is only ML's similarity to paradigm exemplars that contributes to determining looks – thus the lines in ML do not even *thinly* look equal in length, precisely because the diagram is not similar to a paradigm case of equality. However, this precisely amounts to the claim that a certain similarity-relation is selected as that which makes it so that the lines in ML look unequal.

One of Brewer's main contentions against CV is that the selective registration of particular visual similarities is a function of the subject's attention, her interests at the moment, and other such subjective factors, and that this is only intelligible against the background of a relation of acquaintance that does not consist in a categorising, generality-involving activity. However, the discussion of ML brings out that selection is already in place *before* the subject actively engages with the environment and conceptually registers certain things rather than others, insofar as certain similarity-relations are barred from even contributing to the spectrum of *thin looks* (the reflexive similarity of ML, for example). The diagram's similarity to a pair of unequal lines is

selected in perception, thus perception does take a stand (albeit erroneously) on the fact that the two lines are unequal.

The driving motivation behind pure relationalism was to make sense of perception as openness to the world, on an interpretation of that metaphor according to which perception can only be openness to the world if perception does not involve the generality that comes with the notion of content. However, if my analysis of ML is correct, it turns out that, *pace* pure relationalists, it *is* a fact about how perception relates us to the world that certain similarity-relations enjoy a privileged status, as the whole function of paradigm exemplars is to distinguish some similarities as those that determine how an object looks. If certain similarity-relations did not have a privileged status, perception could not have the phenomenal and epistemic determinacy that it in fact has.

5. Generalising Generality

If my argument is correct, there is at least one case in which a purely relationalist account gets things wrong: to make sense of an ML-experience, we have to say that ML is presented as a case of inequality in length, and thus that the property of being unequal in length is *presented as being instantiated*, to put it in Siegel's terms.

One might object that identifying a single a case in which generality is present is not sufficient to rehabilitate CV generally. I am not persuaded by this objection, because it may very well be that generality is always present, but only in a limited number of cases we can clearly see *why* it has to be present.¹⁰ Be that as it may, I think that the case for CV can be made more robust by showing that there is good reason to think that in other, ordinary cases of perpetual experience, generality is in place. In the case of ML, generality is required to make sense of the fact that an ML-experience is illusory. In what follows, I argue that in ordinary cases generality is required to explain how it is that things *veridically* appear as they do. The cases I have in mind involve basic perceptual properties such as colour, shape and size, and in my discussion I draw on the

¹⁰ One could also submit other cases of illusions as evidence that there is a problem with OV. The case of a straight stick in water that looks bent, for example, would raise issues similar to ML.

familiar point that the colour, shape and size of an object typically do not seem to change despite certain variations in light conditions, distance and orientation relative to a perceiver.

I want to start by considering an argument given by Thomas Raleigh (2015) on behalf of pure relationalists against what he calls “the representational model” (1212), which can be treated as equivalent to CV for present purposes.

Raleigh begins with the observation that “It is a long-known fact of optical science that indefinitely many different possible environmental scenes could reflect light onto the retina in exactly the same way”, hence it should be “uncontroversial ... that it would be possible to devise various quite different perceptual scenarios that a subject will not be able to distinguish by looking” (1218). For example, we could, “with sufficient ingenuity and practice”, create a scene in which the subject “is looking at a smaller red disc at closer range or a larger red disc at greater distance” and the subject “would not be able to tell ... these scenes apart by looking” (1219). Again, we could also “use a white disc that is lit with a red light, and we could use all sorts of intrinsically different-shaped ellipses at various angles etc.” (1219). According to Raleigh, these possibilities raise an awkward question for CV (or the representational model):

when things look a certain phenomenal way to me, a way of looking that is bound to be shared by all sorts of very different perceptual scenarios, why think that this way things look represents that any one in particular of these scenarios is the actual environmental scene, rather than any of the other scenarios? (1219)

Let us briefly summarise the argument: according to CV, perceptual experience has accuracy conditions, hence content. But to make this claim good, the CV-theorist should be able to explain why the instantiation of one particular scenario would make the experience accurate, given that there are several alternative scenarios the obtaining of which would not make any difference to one’s phenomenology. Before we proceed, it should also be noted that it is crucial for Raleigh’s argument that the alternative scenarios be relatively *normal*, otherwise the CV-theorist might “rule out all but one of the scenarios as illusory, faulty, misfiring etc.” (1219).

Recall Siegel's image of perception taking a stand. If Raleigh is right, perception could not take a stand on whether the object satisfies a general condition on what it is to be, say, a medium-sized disc at mid-range distance rather than a closer smaller disc: the two scenarios would be indiscriminable, and, because they are both normal, there wouldn't be principled grounds to choose one rather than the other as determining the accuracy conditions of the experience.

I think that there are major problems with Raleigh's argument. First of all, it is striking that there is no mention of *perceptual constancy* in Raleigh's reasoning. Perceptual constancy is the well-known phenomenon in virtue of which we are able to see the colour, shape and size of an object as remaining constant, despite certain variations in light conditions, orientation and distance relative to us. In particular, there is a contrast between the variation at the level of the retinal image as the conditions change on the one hand, and the constancy at the level of experience on the other. Thus, there is a distinct phenomenological dimension to constancy, in the sense that the perceptible properties of objects *look to remain constant* as the conditions of perception and the retinal images change.¹¹ Furthermore, perceptual constancy does not just involve an ability to grasp an object as having *some* indeterminate property or other as the same through variations; it involves grasping some *specific* property or other, and the perceptual scene as a whole contains various cues which help to single out *which* property is grasped as the same through variations. For example, it is usually acknowledged that in an "ordinary sense...a penny looks *round* both when viewed head on and when viewed from an acute angle, even though the area projected by the penny under our retinae under these two conditions is very different" (Cohen 2015: 621, emphasis mine). Again, a person does not seem to grow taller as she approaches near; but she does not seem to be the same *indeterminate* height either: she looks to be a certain approximate height both when she is near and when she is a bit farther away.

Raleigh seems to assume that there is a one-to-one correlation between a given retinal image and a phenomenal look: he begins his argument by noting that indefinitely many

¹¹ See Cohen (2015) for a discussion of the main philosophical and empirical questions raised by perceptual constancy.

different possible environmental scenes could reflect light onto the retina in exactly the same way, and then quickly reaches the conclusion that “there is an entire range of different scenarios that will look the same phenomenal way to a subject when viewed from a given viewpoint” (1219). But this transition goes by far too quickly, for constancy brings out clearly that there is a sense in which our perceptual responses remain the same across *different* perceptual scenarios, so the relation between retinal image and experience is obviously more complex than Raleigh implies.

It might be objected that my reading of Raleigh’s argument is tendentious, for Raleigh claims that “*with sufficient ingenuity and patience*” (1219, emphasis mine), we could create several perceptual scenarios that the subject could not distinguish by looking. But, while I admit that this is true, I do not concede that those would be *normal* scenarios. In what follows, I elaborate on this point.

Let us take as an example the scenario mentioned by Raleigh in which I see a “medium-sized red circular disc, at middle distance, viewed head on” (1219). According to Raleigh, this episode of seeing has the same phenomenology as one in which I see “a smaller red disc closer to me”. However, Raleigh’s claim is only true if we add a major qualification: that there is no way for me or my visual system to take distance into account in the perceptual process, because otherwise it would be perceptually manifest that the two discs are of two different sizes. Thus, a better grasp of the kind of the conditions that would have to obtain for Raleigh’s point to be correct can be achieved by considering the following kind of scenario. Suppose, that one’s visual field was only constituted by a white background and a red dot. Suppose also that at some point the retinal image projected by the dot started shrinking. In this rarefied scenario, one would be unable to tell by looking whether the dot is becoming smaller or rather moving away. However, I think we should emphatically deny that this is a normal scenario.

Why does Raleigh think that the scenarios that he describes are normal?

... my visual system is working just fine and I am seeing things looking just the way that they do in fact look from that perspective. Intuitively, these are all *normal perceptual experiences*. The shared phenomenal way of looking just is how a large

distant red disc looks, *and* how a small close red disc looks, *and* just is how all sorts of different ellipses at a various angles look etc. (1220).

Presumably, Raleigh says that the visual system is working fine because there are no deviant causal chains, the subject is not under the influence of drugs, she has normal eyesight, *etcetera*. And the objects look just like they are supposed to look because, *provided no information about distance (orientation, illumination) is available*, a large disc at a distance certainly looks just like a small disc at a closer distance.

The scenarios Raleigh describes could occur. However, while I do not aim to provide complete conditions for what counts as a normal scenario, it is plausible that there is at least one necessary condition on normality which Raleigh's scenarios lack, because scenarios in which one has absolutely no way of taking into account things like distance, orientation and illumination are by no means normal. Let us say that *rarefied scenarios* are scenarios in which the perceiving subject or her visual system have very little information to go on (for example, a projection on the retina of a dot on a white background, and nothing else). Normal scenarios, by contrast are rich: they contain all sorts of cues that can be used to determine whether an object is actually changing size or simply moving away.¹²

Richness contributes to normality in two related ways: first, rich scenarios are just the scenarios that we happen to experience most of the time. Second, consider the function of our perceptual system: its job is to allow the perceiver to cope with large amounts of data, allow the perceiver to recognise patterns and salient differences, ready the perceiver to respond to affordances of different kinds, etc. Normal scenarios are ones where a perceiver's perceptual systems are dealing with the kind of tasks for which they were selected, and doing so in their usual way (i.e., not deviantly).

Raleigh considers scenarios that are all supposed to be normal and that are phenomenologically indiscriminable from one another, and challenges the CV-theorist

¹² It should be noted that richness is only a necessary, not a sufficient condition for normality: an environment such the Ames room, for example, is reasonably rich, and yet illusory. Thus another plausible candidate condition for normality is that there should not be conflicting cues.

to find a plausible way to argue that only one of the scenarios determine the accuracy conditions of experience because it is the only normal scenario. But in fact *none* of the scenarios considered by Raleigh is normal. By *starting* with artificial, rarefied scenarios, Raleigh inverts the correct order of explanation. Raleigh starts from scenarios in which constancy fails (such as that in which one cannot tell whether a disc is circular or elliptical), and then draws the general conclusion that any one phenomenal way of looking is compatible with an indefinite number of scenarios. But the proper order of explanation would be the following: we do have a fallible capacity for constancy, which, when it works, delivers a univocal verdict as to how things are out there on the basis of a phenomenal way of looking; this capacity can occasionally produce a wrong result, but nothing in this tells against CV.

In order for Raleigh's point to be generally applicable to rich scenarios, not rarefied toy examples, we would need some version of what Matthen labels the *locality thesis* (which he attributes to Helmholtz) namely that "the visual experience occasioned by an object depends solely on the excitation of the retinal neurons onto which that object projects" (Matthen 2010: 228). However, as Matthen goes on to say, we know that "the *same* local retinal response can produce very different observer impressions in different contexts" (235). Contrary to the locality thesis, "the apparent color and shape of an object do not covary with the image *it* projects to the retina taken in isolation ... how an object looks depends on the array of light received by a much larger area of the retina, or perhaps the whole of it" (235). It may well be true, as Raleigh says, that a circular disc at an angle and an elliptical disc seen head on project a similar retinal image. However, in normal, rich perceptual scenarios, the phenomenal look of an object is not solely determined by the light projected by that object, it partly depends on the array of light received from a larger scene: that is why an elliptical disc seen head on normally looks elliptical, whereas a circular disc seen at an angle looks to be circular.¹³

Where does all this leave us with the argument from appearing and, more generally, with the claim that perceptual consciousness entails representational content? Earlier in this paper, I argued that content entails generality, and that ML gives us reason for

¹³ Of course, how our visual system manages to integrate the relevant information is a large research question in the psychology of vision. For useful surveys, see Cohen (2015) and Matthen (2010).

introducing generality in perception. I take it that the discussion of constancy above adds further evidence that perception involves generality.

We can interpret Raleigh as saying that we are presented with objects and properties, and that different scenarios involving differently propertied objects can share the same phenomenal look; and, since there is no reason to discard all but one of the scenarios as illusory, there is no reason to think that perception presents some specific perceptible properties as instantiated either. I have given grounds to doubt this line of thought. Once we reflect on perceptual constancy, we can appreciate that a circular disc seen at an angle is presented *as being circular*, despite its projecting onto the retina of a perceiver the same image as an elliptical disc seen head-on. In normal perceptual scenarios, we are in a position to see that the disc satisfies a certain general condition on what it is to be circular, rather than one on what it is to be elliptical. Furthermore, given that analogous points could be made for colour and size, it turns out that the evidence for conceiving of perception as involving generality is larger than it might *prima facie* appear.

6. Conclusion

I will conclude with two dialectical points. First, in the previous section, I have not argued directly against relationalist models. However, I have argued that in a swathe of central cases there is a form of generality present in perception, insofar as perception takes a stand on the shape, colour and size of particular objects. Given that a central relationalist contention is that perception is wholly particular, this raises problems for relationalists in general.¹⁴

Second, recall that the main relationalist motivation for denying content and the implied generality is that perception is openness to the world. Although I have argued that there actually is generality in perception, I don't mean to say that perception is not openness

¹⁴ It is open in principle that some relationalist other than Brewer might be able to give a satisfactory account of perceptual experience without sneaking in generality. However, it is worth noting two facts: first, Brewer has offered what is by far the most developed and sophisticated account of looks from a purely relationalist perspective, so one might think that if any relationalist account has a good chance, it is probably his. Second, I think that another relationalist, Travis, has great problems dealing with perceptual constancy (I have argued in detail for this in Giananti 2019).

to the world, as there is still a clear sense in which perception is a direct and the most basic access that we have to concrete reality. Spelling out a positive story about perception as openness to the world is of course a large task, but here it might be useful to note at least a few characteristics that are perfectly compatible with CV.¹⁵ First, perception involves causal relations with what is perceived. Second, it has a phenomenology of presence, that is, in perception bits of reality are ostensibly present to us in a way that does not characterise mere thought about reality. In perception, we have a feeling of being in contact with objects that are there in *propria persona*, to use a Husserlian expression (1997, §4).¹⁶ Third, perception grounds singular thoughts: it does not just enable us to think that *some x* at some unspecified place is F, it allows to refer to a particular red object that is in view here and now. Thus what I am rejecting is not that perception is openness to the world, only the pure relationalists' understanding of openness as not involving content and hence generality.

Construing the debate on perception in light of particularity and generality indirectly provides CV with the resources to rehabilitate perceptual content. In this connection, I have argued that we need generality in order to make sense of the phenomenal and the epistemic determinacy of perception. With respect to Siegel's account, my line of reasoning removes an obstacle for the first premise of her argument: if generality's presence in perception best explains central epistemic and phenomenal features of perception, then there being an implicit commitment to generality in the argument from appearing no longer appear problematic. I contend that CV is phenomenologically and epistemologically apt.¹⁷

¹⁵ I have attempted to carry out a fragment of this task in Giananti (2019).

¹⁶ For contemporary elaborations of this Husserlian point, see O'Conaill (2019) and Riccardi (2019).

¹⁷ I am very grateful to Donnchadh O'Conaill for extensive comments on previous versions of this paper. I would also like to thank Bill Brewer, Jorgen Dyrstad, David Jenkins, Gianfranco Soldati and an anonymous referee for *Theoria*. Earlier version of this paper have been presented at a number of workshops, and I wish to thank all the participants for their attention and their questions.

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